

A Study on Mental Health Problems During Menopause and Post-Menopause Middle-Aged Women

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Abstract

Menopause can mark a woman's entry into a new stage of life. It is the stage at which the menstrual cycle permanently ends. A hormonal, physical, and mental transition often occurs during this time between the ages of 40 and 60. These advancements may occur gradually or without warning. Among women going through the menopause, mental health problems such as anxiety, stress, and sadness are documented. The purpose of the current study is to investigate how menopausal symptoms affect middle-aged women's mental health issues, such as anxiety and depression. A basic random selection technique was used to pick 100 middle-aged women between the ages of 45 and 60. Of them, 50 were middle-aged office-going women during menopause and the other 50 were post-menopause. Kumar P. (1992) and Goldberg and Hillier's GHQ-28 and the mental state checklist (MHC) were used to gather data on anxiety and depression. The middle-aged women employed as faculty teachers in the current study had physical symptoms, depression, social dysfunction, and moderate to high levels of stress. Not only did the current tiny study uncover a statistically significant difference between the groups, but it was also intriguing to note that the post-menopausal group had comparatively higher levels of those components than the menopause group had.

Keywords: Menopause, Middle aged women, Depression, Mental health

1.0 Introduction

Menopause is a natural biological process that every person who is born female experiences. Many women suffer from mental health issues as a result of the massive brain gonadal hormone alterations that take place in midlife. The intricate mental health difficulties are poorly understood and managed, and the biological brain hormone alterations are not given much official attention. The current recommendation for treatment is to treat this particular kind of mental illness in the same manner as other mental illnesses. Poor results result for

women and their families as a result of this. Due to menopause-related anxiety and sadness, many women quit their jobs earlier than planned, which results in a loss of income and superannuation.

1.1 Menopause

Menopause can mark the start of a completely new stage in a woman's life. It is the stage at which the menstrual cycle permanently ends. Usually occurring between the ages of 40 and 60, this stage is associated with changes in hormones, the body, and the mind. These advancements may occur gradually or without warning. Women in the menopausal stage report mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, and tension. Hormonal variables are the main causes of midlife problems in females. Depression is partly attributed to climacteric hormonal changes, most notably the reduction in ovarian estrogen production after the menopause. Changes in estrogen levels that occur during menopause are thought to be a possible cause of depression. The term "post-menopause" describes the period of a woman's life that follows menopause. In developed nations, the menopause typically starts between the ages of 40 and 60, while the typical age is 51. In some cases, it will occur earlier due to a medical condition or therapy, such as ovarian evacuation. Many women have physical symptoms associated with the menopause, such as vaginal dryness, hot flashes, night sweats, and decreased drive. It could result in irritability, anxiety, mood swings, and decreased drive.

1.2 Mental Health

One of the most significant aspects of human life is mental wellness. It fulfills a function in both individual lives and the lifespan of society. There is no aspect of human existence that is outside the purview of psychological wellness. The phrase "psychological state" refers to neither a person's personal dimension nor any component of their mental health. "The ability of the individual, the group, and consequently the environment to interact in ways that promote subjective well-being, the best possible development and use of mental abilities (cognitive, affective, and relational), the accomplishment of individual and group goals in accordance with justice, and consequently the realization and maintenance of conditions of fundamental equality" is what is meant to be understood as mental health. (1981) World Health Organizations. Similar to physical health, one's psychological state is a component of their total personality. A mental state can be described as a list that shows how much the person has chosen to meet his environmental needs—be they social, emotional, or physical—and, consequently, how much mental stress he experiences. Indications such as anxiety,

pressure, restlessness, or despondency are common manifestations of psychological or nerves.

2.0 Literature Review

Kothiyal, P., & Sharma, M. (2013). In order to assess knowledge and attitude, carried out a cross-sectional survey on 400 healthy, non-menopausal women between the ages of 40 and 45. The subjects' average attitude score was calculated to be 61.21 ± 12.73 , while their average knowledge score was 63.57 ± 10.79 . 68% of participants in this study had intermediate knowledge, 38.5% had strong knowledge, and 8% had low understanding. In contrast, 81.5% of the female participants expressed confidence in their menopause-related attitudes.

Joshi, M., & Nair, S. (2015). The average age at menopause was 45.9 years (SD - 3.5 years), study on the factors influencing age at natural menopause in 180 women aged 40 to 60 living in rural Punjab. Height progressively raised the average age at menopause, although the differences were not statistically significant. A comparable correlation was observed with BMI, and no discernible pattern was found with education. Additionally, they noted a weakly positive association between the age at menarche and the natural menopause.

Franco, O. H. (2015). The observed discrepancies may be attributed to variations in lifestyle, environmental conditions, education, awareness and concern for the issue, and socioeconomic level. Notable adverse psychological alterations, such as diminished patience, heightened anger, and depression, are also reported in women post-menopause.

Akhtar, T. (2018) investigated menopausal symptoms in women who had just gone through menopause; the study sample's average age was 52.04 ± 5.58 years. Hindus (58%), and literate people (77.1%) made up the majority. Physical symptoms accounted for 75.7% of all reported menopausal symptoms, followed by psychosocial symptoms (63.9% – 49.3%) and vasomotor symptoms (63.5% – 55.4%), with the least amount of reports coming from the sexual domain (42.3% – 36.2%).

Ghosh, D., Singha, P. S., & Parida, P. (2019). The menopausal signs and symptoms varied greatly throughout tribes, study on the drivers of menopausal symptoms in Ghanaian women. Hot flashes (76.4%), mood swings (72.5%), vaginal dryness (71.4%), and night sweats (83.2%) were the most commonly reported menopausal symptoms. Growing older has been linked to a lower risk of experiencing nocturnal sweats. The likelihood of experiencing night

sweats decreased with each unit increase in body weight. The risk of having hot flashes decreased as body fat increased. Hot flushes were not significantly associated with married or single women.

Srikanth, S. (2019). evaluated the average menopausal age of 46.2 ± 1.61 years among rural women in the 40–60 age range. Menstrual discomfort and joint pain (77.5%), hot flashes (62.0%), sleep issues (76.5%), bladder issues (54.5%), and irritability (58.5%) were the most common menopausal symptoms. There was not enough information available about these challenges.

3.0 Objectives of the study

- 1.) To compare middle-aged women during and after menopause in terms of GHQ Sub-scale-1, Anxiety.
- 2.) To compare middle-aged women during and after menopause in terms of GHQ Sub-scale-2, Depression.
- 3.) To compare middle-aged women during and after menopause in terms of GHQ Sub-scale-3, social dysfunction.
- 4.) To determine the disparity in mental health levels between middle-aged women during and after menopause.

4.0 Hypotheses of the study

- 1.) There is no significant difference of Anxiety among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged women.
- 2.) There is no significant difference of Depression among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged women.
- 3.) There is no significant difference of Social Dysfunction among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged office going women.
- 4.) There is no significant difference in Mental Health levels among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged office going women.

5.0 Research method of study

5.1 Sample

The study's sample comprises 100 middle-aged, office-going women, 50 of whom are in the menopause and the other 50 are not. In Delhi, India, in 2018, teachers employed in government-approved girls' schools were chosen at random to comprise the study's sample. They were between the ages of 45 and 60. The middle-aged office-going women ratio was therefore 1:1 during menopause and post-menopause.

5.2 Tools used:

Developed tools have been used during study period. The GHQ-28 by Goldberg and Hillier (and the Mental Health Checklist (MHC) by Kumar P. (1992) were used to collect the data on Anxiety and Depression.

6.0 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Result an Discussion

Table-1: Show the anxiety among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged women

Category	No	Mean	Media n	SD	t-value	Df	Level of significance
During Menopause	50	12.55	13.9	2.18	7.12	98	0.05 Significant
Post Menopause	50	19.19	16	0.89			

Table 1 can be used to interpret the differences in GHQ Sub-scale-1 anxiety levels between middle-aged office-going women going through menopause and those who are not; the calculated mean is 12.55 during menopause and 18.89 post-menopause, while the calculated median is 13.9 during menopause and 15 post-menopause, respectively. The obtained "t" value is 7.12, which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is a significant difference in the anxiety levels of middle-aged office-going women during and after menopause. The standard deviation for menopause is 2.18 and 0.89, respectively. We therefore reject our hypothesis H1, which stated that there is no substantial difference in anxiety between middle-aged women going through menopause and those who have gone through it. Instead, we propose that there is a significant difference in anxiety between middle-aged women going through menopause and those who have gone through it.

Table No. 02 Show the Depression among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged women

Category	No	Mean	Media n	SD	t-value	df	Level of significance
During Menopause	50	12.89	15	1.69	6.02	98	0.05 Significant
Post Menopause	50	16.01	16	1.21			

Table 2 can be used to interpret the differences in GHQ Sub-scale-2 Depression between middle-aged women who are going through menopause and those who are not. The calculated mean is 12.89 during menopause and 16.01 during post-menopause, respectively, while the calculated median is 15 during menopause and 16 during post-menopause. The obtained "t" value is 6.02, which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is a significant difference between middle-aged office-going women experiencing depression during menopause and post-menopause. The standard deviation for menopause is 1.69 and 1.21, respectively. Therefore, our hypothesis H2, which claimed that there was no discernible difference in Depression between middle-aged office-going women going through menopause and those who had gone through post-menopause, is rejected. Instead, it should be rephrased to say that there is a discernible difference in Depression between those women.

Table No. 03 Show the Social Dysfunction among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged women

Category	No	Mean	Media n	SD	t-value	df	Level of significance
During Menopause	50	15.26	14	1.69	6.24	98	0.05 Significant
Post Menopause	50	16.79	15	1.21			

Table 3 provides an analysis of the differences in GHQ Sub-scale-3 Social Dysfunction between middle-aged office-going women during and after menopause. The calculated mean is 15.26 during menopause and 16.79 post-menopause, while the median is 14 during menopause and 15 post-menopause, respectively. The obtained 't' value is 6.24, which is significant at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is a significant difference between middle-aged office-going women during and after menopause in terms of social dysfunction. The standard deviation is 1.69 for women during menopause and 1.21 for women after menopause. Consequently, our hypothesis H3, which claimed that middle-aged office-going women experiencing menopause and post-menopause did not significantly differ in terms of social dysfunction, is rejected. Instead, it should be rephrased to say that there is a significant difference in social dysfunction between these groups of women.

Table No. 04 Show the Mental Health level among Menopause and Post Menopause middle-aged women

Category	No	Mean	Media	SD	t-value	df	Level of
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			n				significance
During Menopause	50	18.69	18	4.21	8.33	98	0.05 Significant
Post Menopause	50	29.83	30	6.35			

Table -04 analysis allows us to compare the mental health levels of middle-aged office-going women during and after menopause. The calculated mean is 18.69 during menopause and 29.83 post-menopause, respectively, while the calculated median is 18 during menopause and 30 post-menopause. The obtained-value is 8.33, which is significant at the 0.05 or 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is a significant difference between the mental health of middle-aged office-going women during and after menopause. The S.D. for menopause is 4.21, and for post-menopause it is 6.35. Therefore, our hypothesis H6, which claimed that there was no discernible difference in the mental health of middle-aged office-going women during and after menopause, is rejected. Instead, it should be rephrased to claim that there is a discernible difference in the mental health of these women.

7.0 Conclusion

Due to hormonal changes, women experience biological changes throughout the menopause and the post-menopause in their middle age. These changes may have an impact on their social, psychological, and physical health. In a middle-aged office-going woman who was also a school teacher, the current study found moderate to high levels of anxiety, sadness, social dysfunction, and psychosomatic symptoms. It was intriguing to observe that the post-menopausal group had relatively higher levels of these components than the menopause group had, and the current modest study was able to identify a statistically significant difference between the groups.

Women's changes between the ages of 40 and 60 demand careful consideration. Ideally, working women could need more attention because they have two roles to fulfill. Managing all of the exercises with the same productivity as in the past may prove to be a little challenging. These working women could experience guilt, annoyance, stress, etc. as a result. Sound living necessitates physical relaxation, eager assistance, and fundamental thought. A few lifestyle changes and altered prayers can boost their good, virtuous tendencies, lessen stress, and improve the quality of their lives.

References

1. Aqeel, M., Arbab, K. B., & Akhtar, T. (2018). Psychological problems and its association to other symptoms in menopausal transition. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 33(2), 507-519.
2. Batool, S., Kausar, R., Naqvi, G., Javed, A., & Tufail, H. (2017). Menopausal Attitude and Symptoms in Peri and Post-Menopausal Working Women. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 32(1).
3. Beigi, M., & Fahami, F. (2012). A comparative study on sexual dysfunctions before and after menopause. *Iranian journal of nursing and midwifery research*, 17(2 Suppl1), S72-S75.
4. Elavsky, S., & McAuley, E. (2009). Personality, menopausal symptoms, and physical activity outcomes in middle-aged women. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 46(2), 123-128.
5. Ghosh, D., Singha, P. S., & Parida, P. (2019). Postmenopausal health of Indian women: A review. *Current Women's Health Reviews*, 15(1), 64-69.
6. Joshi, M., & Nair, S. (2015). Epidemiological study to assess the menopausal problems during menopausal transition in middle age women of Vadodara, Gujarat, India. *Indian J Obstet Gynaecol Res*, 2(3), 163-8.
7. Judd, F. K., Hickey, M., & Bryant, C. (2012). Depression and midlife: are we overpathologising the menopause?. *Journal of affective disorders*, 136(3), 199-211.
8. Kim, J., & Ahn, S. (2016). Impact of menopausal status, metabolic syndrome and its risk factors on impaired quality of life above middle-aged women. *Korean Journal of Women Health Nursing*, 22(4), 275-286.
9. Kothiyal, P., & Sharma, M. (2013). Post-menopausal quality of life and associated factors. *Journal of Scientific and Innovative Research*, 2(4), 814-823.
10. Kwak, E. K., Park, H. S., & Kang, N. M. (2014). Menopause knowledge, attitude, symptom and management among midlife employed women. *Journal of menopausal medicine*, 20(3), 118.
11. Masjoudi, M., Amjadi, M. A., & Leyli, E. K. N. (2017). Severity and frequency of menopausal symptoms in middle aged women, Rasht, Iran. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*, 11(8), QC17.
12. Mohammad-Alizadeh-Charandabi, S., Rezaei, N., Hakimi, S., & Montazeri, A. (2012). Predictors of health-related quality of life in postmenopausal women: a population-based study. *Journal of caring sciences*, 1(4), 201.

13. Newhart, M. R. (2013). Menopause matters: The implications of menopause research for studies of midlife health. *Health Sociology Review, 22*(4), 365-376.
14. Poomalar, G. K., & Arounassalame, B. (2013). The quality of life during and after menopause among rural women. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR, 7*(1), 135.
15. Sudha, B. P., & Vijayanchali, S. S. (2013). HEALTH PROBLEMS OF POST MENOPAUSAL WOMEN. *Journal of Research Extension and Development (JRED), 1*, 86-88.
16. Surendar, R., Durgapriya, G., Arthi, M., & Srikanth, S. (2019). Quality of life among post-menopausal women in rural Puducherry. *Public Health Review: International Journal of Public Health Research, 6*(3), 112-118.
17. Terauchi, M., Hiramitsu, S., Akiyoshi, M., Owa, Y., Kato, K., Obayashi, S., ... & Kubota, T. (2012). Associations between anxiety, depression and insomnia in peri-and post-menopausal women. *Maturitas, 72*(1), 61-65.
18. Van Dijk, G. M., Kavousi, M., Troup, J., & Franco, O. H. (2015). Health issues for menopausal women: the top 11 conditions have common solutions. *Maturitas, 80*(1), 24-30.